

Monolayer $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ -Based Photodetectors Grown by Chemical Vapor Deposition

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The utilization of alloyed 2D transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) has become a pivotal approach for addressing challenges in material applications. The judicious selection of dopant constituents offers a potent means to finely modulate the materials' bandgap, consequently broadening the potential applications of 2D materials. In the context of an investigation, $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ is successfully synthesized using chemical vapor deposition. With a bandgap of 1.33 eV, this material exhibits promising prospects for application in the realm of optoelectronics. This advancement enables the fabrication of the $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ photodetector. The rigorous testing and analysis of photoelectric performance reveal significant improvements in both responsivity and response speed compared to analogous detectors. This accomplishment not only furnishes a novel paradigm for the advancement of photodetectors but also contributes fresh insights to the domain of alloyed 2D TMDs.

1. Introduction

Graphene, a 2D material composed of single-layer carbon atoms, has marked a significant advancement in the exploration of 2D materials.^[1–3] Despite its impressive electrical and thermal conductivity, the characteristic of zero bandgap restricts its potential in the semiconductor realm. To address the demands of contemporary electronics, researchers have initiated a quest for alternative 2D materials.^[4–7] Through dedicated investigation, novel materials, like transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs), MXene, and h-BN, have emerged, boasting superior physical and chemical attributes compared to graphene.^[8–12] These materials have garnered substantial attention as focal points of research within the realm of 2D materials.^[6,13–15]

Molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) is a prominent TMD. Sulfur (S) and molybdenum (Mo) elements combine to form a layered sandwich structure denoted as S—Mo—S. It is characterized by robust intra-layer chemical bonds and relatively weak interlayer van der Waals forces, resulting in a stable intra-layer structure and fragile interlayer connections, allowing facile exfoliation (similar TMDs include WS_2 , ReS_2 , WS_2 , and MoSe_2).^[16,17] Its bandgap, influenced by layer count, decreases from 1.8 eV for single-layer MoS_2 to ≈ 0.8 eV in bulk MoS_2 .^[18] MoS_2 's favorable characteristics, including high carrier mobility and stability, make it versatile for applications in electronic components like photodetectors and metal oxide semiconductor field effect transistors (MOSFETs).^[19] Currently, based on MoS_2 , exploration has expanded to ternary ($\text{Mo}_{1-x}\text{Re}_x\text{S}_2$,^[20] $\text{Mo}_{1-x}\text{W}_x\text{S}_2$,^[21] $\text{MoS}_{2(1-x)}\text{Se}_{2x}$)^[22] and quaternary variants ($\text{Mo}_x\text{W}_{(1-x)}\text{S}_{2y}\text{Se}_{2(1-y)}$).^[23] The notable electrical conductivity and thermal stability of these materials make them suitable for a variety of application contexts.

Nevertheless, certain limitations characterize 2D molybdenum disulfide, with defects within its layered structure emerging as a paramount concern.^[24] Such defects encompass vacancies, impurities, and assorted structurally anomalous regions.^[25,26] These deviations wield substantial influence over the physical, chemical, and electrical traits of 2D molybdenum disulfide. Notably, they disrupt electron transport pathways, thereby

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Figure 1. a) Schematic of growth procedure for quaternary alloys. b) I,II) Illustration of $\text{MoO}_3/\text{ReO}_3/\text{WO}_3$ deposition step. III,IV) Illustration of $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ growth step. c) Optical image of as-grown triangular monolayer quaternary alloys (size = 60 μm). d) AFM images of monolayer $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ grown at 900 $^\circ\text{C}$. e) Cross-sectional projection electron microscopy image of $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ on Si/SiO₂ substrate (TEM). f–i) Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) mapping of the four elements of Re, Mo, W, and S. Scale bars: (f–i) 8 nm.

imparting alterations to their electrical attributes. Furthermore, defects exert discernible effects on the material's optical absorption and emission characteristics, thereby casting an impact on its photoelectric performance. Practical applications also confront hurdles necessitating resolution such as augmenting carrier mobility and conductivity. Therefore, comprehensive exploration remains imperative regarding the stability and endurance of molybdenum sulfide, ensuring its sustained effectiveness and dependability throughout prolonged usage.^[27,28]

Chemical doping emerges as a pivotal strategy for the modification of MoS_2 .^[29–32] This process entails the introduction of impurity elements into MoS_2 , thereby inducing alterations in its structure and properties.^[22,33–36] These impurity elements encompass diverse metal ions, non-metal ions, and even rare earth elements.^[37,38] Through the doping process, these impurity elements replace molybdenum or sulfur atoms within MoS_2 , triggering charge transfers and consequential structural transformations.^[39–42] Concurrently, the introduction of dopants or manipulation of environmental conditions can mitigate or eliminate material defects, culminating in the creation of premium-quality 2D MoS_2 specimens.^[43–45] Such modifications exert discernible impacts on the material's electrical, magnetic, and catalytic characteristics, thus fostering heightened performance and wider applicability.^[46–49] Primary techniques of elemental chemical doping encompass the ion exchange method, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method, solution synthesis method, and radiation doping method.^[50–52] For instance, researchers harnessed the CVD approach to infuse rhenium into MoS_2 , which improved the responsiveness of the

photodetector.^[53] Others adopted ion implantation to introduce tungsten (W) for high-speed detector fabrication,^[21,54,55] while some introduced niobium (Nb) for crafting high-performance transistors.^[56] Additionally, the incorporation of the non-metallic element nitrogen (N) aimed to enhance light absorption and bolster photoelectric conversion efficiency.^[57] By judiciously selecting doping constituents, regulating doping concentration and distribution, synergizing with other modification methodologies, and refining fabrication processes, the photoelectric capabilities of MoS_2 can experience further enhancements.^[58] Such advancements expand the realm of possibilities for employing MoS_2 in photovoltaic conversion and optoelectronic devices.^[59]

In this work, monolayer $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ films were synthesized by the CVD method using a certain proportion of sulfur, MoO_3 , WO_3 , and ReO_3 powders in a high temperature, and then Raman spectroscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis of the resulting alloy materials were performed. In order to further study the optoelectronic properties of the synthesized $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$, the structure of the quaternary material was simulated, the change of the band gap was calculated, and then a photodetector based on the $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ was fabricated, which achieved high performance.

2. Result and Discussion

$\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ flakes were synthesized through the CVD technique, as illustrated in **Figure 1a** (for a detailed procedure, refer to the Experimental Section). In the growth dynamics of 2D materials via CVD, three crucial physical parameters come into

Figure 2. a) Raman spectroscopy of the pure MoS₂ and the W, Re-doped MoS₂. b–d) Raman mapping of alloys grown at 900 °C (from the selection in figure b). e) The Raman shift of E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} as a function for temperature, including the value of χ obtained from linear fitting. f–i) XPS spectrum of f) Mo 3d peaks and g) S 2p peaks in W-doped MoS₂ and pure MoS₂, h) W 4f peaks in W, Re-doped MoS₂. i) Re 4f peaks in W, Re-doped MoS₂.

play: adatom diffusion on the substrate, edge kinetics, and precursor flux.^[60] These factors collectively govern the growth process and the resulting properties of the synthesized material. In Figure 1b, four distinct reaction steps illustrate the synthesis process. A constant amount of oxide is maintained while the deposition temperature is altered during the oxide deposition step. Excess oxide molecules are carried away from the reaction zone by the Ar carrier gas, ensuring a constant oxide deposition after the process. As for sulfur, it transforms into the gas phase at higher temperatures and is then driven to the reaction zone by the carrier gas, where it reacts with the oxide molecules adsorbed on the substrate, leading to the formation of the new material. This research maintained a constant precursor concentration while varying the growth temperature. Optical images in Figure S2a–h, Supporting Information, display the samples grown at 800, 850, 900, and 950 °C, respectively, exhibiting distinct morphologies. It is evident from the optical images that the grown Mo_{1-x-y}Re_xW_yS₂ material exhibits superior morphology at a growth temperature of 900 °C. Raman spectra of Re_{0.15}W_{0.05}Mo_{0.80}S₂ film grown by CVD under different temperatures (800, 850, 900, and 950 °C) in Figure S3a,b, Supporting Information. At 900 °C, the FWHM of A_{1g} and E_{2g}¹ peaks are minimized, indicating that the material grown at this temperature has fewer defects and is more stable. In Figure 1c,d, the optical image and high-magnification atomic force microscope (AFM) image of the monolayer Mo_{1-x-y}Re_xW_yS₂ (as-grown sample at 900 °C) are presented. The surface roughness of the material was analyzed using high-magnification AFM images, revealing a roughness value of R_a = 0.251 nm. To further investigate the growth effects,

a cross-sectional transmission electron microscope (TEM) image of the film on the Si/SiO₂ substrate is shown in Figure 1e, confirming that Mo_{1-x-y}Re_xW_yS₂ is a monolayer with a thickness of ≈0.54 nm. For further verification of the elemental composition in the Mo_{1-x-y}Re_xW_yS₂ film, energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) mapping was conducted. The EDX mapping results, shown in Figure 1f–i, reveal the distribution of the four elements Mo, Re, W, and S in the film. Mo, Re, W, and S are represented by orange, purple, red, and gray, respectively. It is evident that the distribution of these elements in the synthesized film is not uniform, and the figure shows the spatial segregation of various elements.

To conduct a more in-depth analysis of the material composition, Raman spectroscopy was utilized to study the composition of the alloy that was produced and also create spatial maps of specific Raman vibrational modes. In Figure 2a, the grown state sample the grown state sample exhibits two distinct peaks, E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g}, with A_{1g} doping causing a red-shifted peak position toward the long wave direction. This red-shift is attributed to the homogeneous alloying of Mo-W-Re and changes in vibrational modes after doping. Additionally, the E_{2g}¹ peak becomes higher compared to the A_{1g} peak, indicating an increase in electron concentration. The combined changes of A_{1g} and E_{2g}¹ suggest that Re doping introduces a significant number of electrons. According to literature, Re doping causes a red shift in the peak position, while W doping causes a blue shift. However, in this experiment, the peak position is red-shifted, and the height difference between E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} becomes smaller, though not exceeding A_{1g}. This suggests that both Re and W are involved in regulating the synthesis process, with Re doping having a more significant

Figure 3. a) 3D schematic and master view of the $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$. b) High-resolution STEM image of monolayer as grown sample at 900°C . c) The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern. d) Enlarged view of the red selection in (b). e) Intensity profile of the material. Re and W atoms are identified by the intensity profile.

impact than W doping. Figure 2c,d represents Raman mapping of the specific area indicated in Figure 2b. Based on the Raman mapping shown in Figure 2c,d, it is evident that there is a slight deviation from compositional homogeneity at the two Raman peaks. This phenomenon can be attributed to the alteration in the composition of MoS_2 due to doping and the possible presence of small amounts of defects in the $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$. However, there were no significant compositional differences observed in the Raman mapping, indicating a high degree of alloying and material stability in the doped material. To assess $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$'s stability, Raman peak level tests were performed during a temperature change from 300 to 400 K, as shown in Figure 2e. The change in peak position is attributed to the thermal expansion of $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ resulting from an increase in temperature. Furthermore, the incorporation of impurity atoms induces changes in the structure of MoS_2 , leading to a higher first-order temperature coefficient compared to the pristine material. At this point, the $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$'s entropy increases, enhancing its stability. Despite these alterations, they do not significantly affect the thermal stability of $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$. Therefore, it can be concluded that this material exhibits outstanding thermal stability.

XPS measurements were conducted to investigate the influence of W and Re ions in MoS_2 . The XPS analysis confirmed the precise composition of each alloy sample and preliminarily analyzed their electronic structure (Figure 2f–i). Figure 2f–i shows the Mo 3d peaks and S 2p peaks of W, Re-doped and pure MoS_2 , W 4f peaks, and Re 4f peaks of W, Re-doped MoS_2 . Previous research indicates that W introduces hole features in MoS_2 . In Figure 2f, it is observed that red-shifts in the binding energy characteristic peaks of Mo 3d and blue-shifts in the binding energy characteristic peaks of S 2p after Re and W-doping. Specifically, Mo 3d_{3/2} shifts from 233.08 to 232.93 eV, and Mo 3d_{5/2} shifts from 229.91 to 229.71 eV. Additionally, S 2p_{1/2} shifts from 163.99 to 164.07 eV, S 2p_{3/2} + 2p_{1/2} shifts from 162.78 to 162.82 eV, S 2p_{3/2} shifts from 161.25 to 161.58 eV, respectively (Figure 2g). In Figure 2h,i, the peak of W 4f appears at 31.20 eV. The peaks of Re 4f_{7/2} and 4f_{5/2} are located at 41.45 and 43.83 eV, respectively. This indicates the successful doping of Re and W atoms. It is the doping of both types of atoms that leads to the shift observed in

the XPS peaks of Mo and S. The existing studies reveal that Re-doped MoS_2 shows red-shifted Mo 3d characteristic peaks and blue-shifted S 2p characteristic peaks, indicating the formation of n-type doping as the Fermi energy level moves away from the valence band. On the other hand, when W is doped into MoS_2 , the Mo 3d characteristic peaks also exhibit red-shifts, while the S 2p peaks show red-shifts as well. This suggests the formation of p-type doping, possibly due to the substitutional W ions possessing fewer valence electrons and more holes compared to Mo ions (work function: W:4.5 eV, Mo:4.37 eV). In our study, after the co-doping of Re and W, it is observed that red-shifted Mo 3d characteristic peaks and blue-shifted S 2p characteristic peaks, indicating that the Fermi energy level is considerably away from the valence band. Therefore, it can be inferred that the content of Re is higher than the content of W. Based on the analysis of the measured composition, the new material's composition was determined as $\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$.

The 3D image of Figure 3a illustrates an inhomogeneous doping pattern of Re with W elements, mainly doped by replacing the position of Mo atoms. To investigate the intricate atomic distribution of elements in this complex quaternary 2D system, the 900 °C as-grown samples are examined using a Nion aberration-corrected Ultra STEM 100, operating with an accelerating voltage of 120 kV. Figure 3b presents a typical atomic-resolution scanning transmission electron microscopy with an annular dark-field (STEM-ADF) image of a monolayer $\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{S}_2$ flake, exhibiting the characteristic 2H structure. The 2H polymorphism is further verified by the corresponding fast Fourier transform (FFT) pattern (Figure 3c), which reveals a perfect hexagonal lattice. The lattice constant of 2H- $\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$ is measured at ≈ 3.2 Å (Figure 3d), which greatly resembles the pristine 2H- MoS_2 . Distinguishing the metal site from the chalcogenide site can be achieved by analyzing a histogram of the intensities associated with each of these distinct sites. This histogram will help in characterizing and differentiating the relative abundance or concentration of these sites within the material. Figure 3d,e shows the atomically resolved HR-STEM image with Z-contrast ($Z_{\text{Re}} = 75$, $Z_{\text{W}} = 74$, $Z_{\text{Mo}} = 42$, and $Z_{\text{S}} = 16$) for the doped sample, which shows a clear hexagonal lattice structure for the sample. Due to

Figure 4. a) Formation energy of W doping MoS₂ and Re doping in MoS₂ under S-poor and S-rich conditions. b) Density of states (DOS) calculations for the intrinsic and W-Re co-doped MoS₂. c, d) Band structures of the intrinsic MoS₂ and Re_{0.15}W_{0.05}Mo_{0.80}S₂.

a nearly identical Z atomic number between W ($Z = 74$) and Re ($Z = 75$), differentiating W and Re remains challenging by STEM Z-contrast images.

To determine the synthesis and bandgap characteristics of the new-obtained sample, we performed first-principles calculations of the formation energy and bandgap changes. As shown in **Figure 4a**, the formation energy of the W-doping and Re-doping defects are presented under S-poor and S-rich conditions. Under S-poor conditions, the formation energies for both Re and W doping defects are high, indicating that doping is difficult to achieve. However, under S-rich conditions, the formation energies decrease dramatically, indicating that doping becomes energetically favorable and the formation of the doped material could be promoted. Additionally, when in a high concentration of S carrier gas, it can be observed that the formation energy of Re doping is significantly lower than that of W doping. Therefore, the feature of formation energies is consistent with the experimental results and explains the higher doping of Re in the sample.

Figure 4b shows the varied DOS after Re and W co-doping compared to the undoped MoS₂. The Re-W co-doped MoS₂ exhibits n-type doping with the Fermi level crossing the conduction band minimum (CBM), which is consistent with the experimental results indicating that Re doping introduces electrons into the material. Additionally, **Figures 4c,d** show the intrinsic band structure and the unfolded band structure of the co-doped structure, respectively, where the bandgap values are clearly represented. The intrinsic MoS₂ shows a direct bandgap of 1.66 eV. However, after doping with Re and W, the bandgap decreases to 1.33 eV and maintains the direct bandgap feature. Additionally, the band structure of the co-doped MoS₂ is observed to be n-type doping, indicating the introduction of more electrons into the material.

Therefore, Re and W doping can be used to effectively control the bandgap of MoS₂.

In recent years, 2D TMDs have exhibited remarkable photoelectric conversion properties, particularly in photodetector applications. To investigate the photoelectric characteristics of the recently synthesized Mo_{1-x-y}Re_xW_yS₂ material, Mo_{1-x-y}Re_xW_yS₂ photodetectors were fabricated on n-Si/SiO₂, as depicted in **Figure 5a**. Employing electron beam lithography (EBL) equipment, we designed finger electrodes with narrower trench spacing to optimize their optoelectronic performance. This strategic use of fork-finger electrodes simultaneously enhances the photodetector's effective area, further amplifying its optoelectronic capabilities. The photodetector's photoelectric properties were subsequently tested at a bias voltage of 1 V. The initial assessment involved measuring the dark current (I_{dark}) under dark conditions, revealing a dark current magnitude of $\approx 1 \mu\text{A}$ at 1 V bias. This observation signifies the presence of uninhibited electron flow within the material, a quality that is also advantageous for field-effect transistor (FET) studies. Upon irradiation with a 365 nm laser, the photodetector's photoelectric response was evaluated at 10% intervals starting from 100%, as indicated in **Figure 5b**. The results illustrate a noteworthy order of magnitude increase in photocurrent relative to the dark current subsequent to laser irradiation. This disparity in current at a 1 V bias voltage is striking. The laser's effect lies in its ability to excite additional free electrons within the material, a phenomenon facilitated by the substantial influx of electrons due to the doping of Re, W atoms.^[20] Consequently, this leads to an elevation in photocurrent attributed to the augmented population of excited electrons. Furthermore, the enhancement in photocurrent also exhibits a minor hole contribution, stemming from the presence of molybdenum vacancies evident in TEM images. These findings collectively underscore the intricate interplay of doping and material vacancies, contributing to the observed photoelectric improvements.

Subsequently, the curve of the detector current versus time ($I-V, t$) was evaluated under a bias voltage of 1 V and a light intensity of 365 nm, as depicted in **Figure 5c**. The photodetector's response exhibited notable acceleration in the presence of the 365 nm light intensity. To gain a closer perspective, a local zoom-in analysis was performed, as presented in **Figure 5d**. Response time is usually defined as the time taken by 10% to 90% of the net photocurrent. From the localized zoom of **Figure 5d**, it is evident that both the rise time and fall time of the material amount to 0.160 s, reflecting a substantial improvement in comparison to the response time of MoS₂. This marked enhancement can be attributed primarily to the synergistic doping of rhenium and tungsten, which contributes to the partial filling of vacancies generated during the growth process. The presence of vacancies within the material results in the confinement of free electrons, generating an electron-trapping effect. This effect extends the lifetime of carriers, thereby enhancing optical responsivity. However, it introduces a critical drawback for detectors reliant on responsiveness.^[21,55] Consequently, a reduction in vacancies directly translates to a shorter carrier lifetime, facilitating a swifter response and consequently a higher-speed performance. Collectively, by comparison with other TMDCs photodetectors (refer to **Figure S4**, Supporting Information), the comprehensive test outcomes underscore that the incorporation of rhenium and

Figure 5. a) Schematic diagram of the $\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$ photodetector. b) Current versus incident powers curve of $\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$ photodetector illuminated by 365 nm wavelength light. Device performance changes of $\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$ photodetector, which were measured at a wavelength of 365 nm. c,d) The occurrence of photocurrent in repeated dark and light environments. c) Photocurrent versus time curve of $\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$ photodetector illumination. The corresponding rise time and fall time are shown in panel (d). The performance of the $\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$ photodetector varies with the change of the incident power including e) photocurrent and responsivity, and f) noise equivalent power and normalized detectivity.

tungsten co-doping in MoS_2 yields dual benefits: it improves the responsivity while significantly increasing the speed of response.

Conclusively, the assessment of the photodetector's efficacy is conducted through pertinent parameters, graphically depicted in Figure 5e,f. A pivotal measure of its photoconversion attributes is the responsivity (R), calculated as $R = I_{\text{ph}}/(P_{\text{in}}S)$. Here, I_{ph} signifies the photocurrent, S denotes the effective illuminated area of the heterojunction plane, and P_{in} represents the incident light's power density. The quantification of the photodetector's detection prowess is encapsulated by the noise equivalent power (NEP) and the specific detection rate (D^*). Superior detection capability corresponds to lower NEP and higher D^* values. The evaluation of NEP and D^* can be executed employing the following equations: $\text{NEP} = (2qI_{\text{dark}}\Delta f)^{1/2}/R$ and $D^* = A^{1/2}/\text{NEP}$. Within these expressions, I_{dark} characterizes the dark-state current, Δf signifies the bandwidth (set at 1 in this instance), and A pertains to the active device area. Notably, the calculated active area (A) stands at $506 \mu\text{m}^2$, referencing the face-to-face region of the two electrodes. Remarkably, as depicted in the figures, the responsivity diminishes with escalating optical power. This phenomenon arises from the saturation of photoelectron absorption at low optical power levels, leading to a plateau in responsivity despite increased light intensity. This observation underscores the photodetectors' sustained excellence even under conditions of subdued light. It exhibits an

exceptionally heightened sensitivity, manifested by NEP values as diminutive as $1.28 \times 10^{-15} \text{ W Hz}^{-1/2}$, and an extraordinary detection capability, evidenced by D^* values reaching up to 1.76×10^{10} Jones.

3. Conclusion

In summary, we have successfully synthesized a novel quaternary material ($\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$) by incorporating rhenium and tungsten into molybdenum sulfide through a doping process. Various characterization techniques were used to verify the presence and composition of each element in the new material. Additionally, utilizing STEM-ADF imaging, confirmed the stable 2H phase structure of the single-layer material. Through density functional theory (DFT) calculations, it investigated the variation in the band gap of $\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$ and conducted a comprehensive analysis to elucidate the underlying reasons for these changes. Importantly, $\text{Re}_{0.15}\text{W}_{0.05}\text{Mo}_{0.80}\text{S}_2$ displayed exceptional photoelectric properties even under ambient conditions, exhibiting a remarkable responsivity of 405.97 A W^{-1} and an impressively rapid response time of 0.160 s. Comparative assessment with similar photoelectric detectors underscored the substantial advancements of our material, showcasing substantial enhancements in both response rate and response speed. This research

opens up novel avenues for the development of TMDs, leveraging tailored content ratios of distinct elements to explore innovative possibilities in the field.

4. Experimental Section

Material Synthesis: The monolayer $\text{Mo}_{1-x-y}\text{Re}_x\text{W}_y\text{S}_2$ (0.54 nm) was epitaxially grown on Si/SiO₂ substrates using the CVD method (SK-G05123K-3-655, TIANJIN ZHONGHUAN FURNACE Corp., China). Sulfur powder (1.40 g) was placed in the alumina combustion boat upstream of the quartz tubular furnace. Molybdenum trioxide powder (MoO₃, 99.95%), tungsten trioxide powder (WO₃, 99.95%), and rhenium trioxide powder (ReO₃, 99.95%) were evenly dispersed in the alumina crucible and placed in the center of the furnace. Then, cleaned Si/SiO₂ substrates (1 cm × 1 cm) were placed directly on top of the MoO₃, WO₃, and ReO₃ powder in the alumina crucible boat. After the position was fixed, repeated pumping cycles were carried out to remove impurity gases in the furnace tube, and the reaction was further continued under optimized conditions in an Ar ambient. After the reaction, the furnace was naturally cooled to room temperature under 120 sccm of Ar.

Characterization Methods: Raman spectroscopy was performed using the Confocal Renishaw system (512 nm, 0.25 mW). Cross-sectional samples were prepared by FIB (FEI-G4) to directly observe the vertical morphology. TEM testing was conducted using the America FEI-Titan Cubed Themis G2 300, and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis was performed using its related equipment. Topography and surface potential images were measured using a Bruker ICON AFM in Scanasyt mode.

DFT Simulations: All the calculations were performed based on the projector-augmented wave (PAW) method as implemented in the Vienna ab-initio simulation package (VASP). The general gradient approximation with the exchange and correlation interaction of Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (GGA-PBE) was adopted to optimize the system geometry. The cutoff energy of the plane-wave basis was set to be 500 eV. The lattice and atomic positions were fully relaxed based on the conjugate gradient algorithm until the Hellmann–Feynman forces were less than 0.01 eV Å⁻¹, and the total energy convergence criterion was set to be 10⁻⁵ eV. The Brillouin zone (BZ) was represented by Gamma-centered unit cells with 3 × 4 × 1 Monkhorst–Pack k-point mesh for geometry optimizations. In order to eliminate the periodic image interaction, a vacuum layer of 20 Å was constructed perpendicular to the layer plane.

The formation energy of a neutral doping defect is computed from

$$E^f = E_{\text{doping}} + E_{\text{Mo}} - E_{\text{MoS}_2} - E_X \quad (1)$$

where E_{Mo} and E_X are the energy of one atom of the bulk metal Mo and (X = Re, W); E_{MoS_2} is the total energy of MoS₂ and E_{doping} is the total energy of MoS₂ with the dopant on a Mo lattice site.

Fabrication and Measurement of the Devices: The Si/SiO₂ substrate underwent a pre-cleaning process, which included 10 min of acetone, 10 min of isopropanol, and 10 min of deionized water ultrasonic cleaning steps to remove organic residues. Then, the Re_{0.15}W_{0.05}Mo_{0.80}S₂ thin film layer was grown on the cleaned substrate by the CVD method. Finally, Cr/Au (5 nm/50 nm) was deposited to form the anode. The electrical and optical performance of photodetectors, including *I*–*V* characteristics and *I*–*T* characteristics, was measured using a Keithley 4200-SCS semiconductor analyzer on a probe station. To describe the electrical characteristics of the fabricated Re_{0.15}W_{0.05}Mo_{0.80}S₂ diode, *I*–*V* measurements were performed in the ±1 V range.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

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